

conditions described. This was indicated by rapid attainment of equilibrium during the course of titration and by the absence of any significant drift in pH even after two hours. This was further confirmed by taking tit of a sample titration mixture from time to time.

In the ligand, it is the phenolic OH group that takes part in complex formation and the proton is replaced from it by the metal ion during chelation. As only one proton per ligand molecule is liberated, 'Y' the number of dissociable protons attached to each ligand molecule is one.

From the titration curves (Fig. 1), $\bar{n}_A$ values at various B values (pH meter readings) were calculated and the formation curve (B vs $\bar{n}_A$) was plotted. The pK_H^A corresponding to phenolic H was obtained by half integral method at $\bar{n}_A=0.5$. This was further corroborated by plotting the graph of $\log(\bar{n}_A/1-\bar{n}_A)$ vs B.

Fig. 1. Titration curves of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-sulphamethoxazole.

From the titration curves, $\bar{n}$ and pL values for metal-ligand systems were also determined. Values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were determined from the curves $\bar{n}$ vs pL by half integral method and the results were corroborated by plotting the graph of $\left[\log \frac{\bar{n}}{1-\bar{n}} \right]$ vs pL . As in the cases of Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Mg^{2+} complexes the difference between $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ was found to be less than 1.78 log units, these were computed by the least square method, and the results are reported in Table 1.

TABLE 1—STEPWISE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF VARIOUS COMPLEXES*

Cations	t = 25°		μ = 0.1			
	H ⁺	Cu ²⁺	Zn ²⁺	Ni ²⁺	Co ²⁺	Mg ²⁺
log K ₁	8.18	7.56	6.58	4.18	3.90	2.94
log K ₂	—	6.03	5.50	—	—	2.87

* The order of stability of metal chelates is found to be $Cu^{2+} > Zn^{2+} > Ni^{2+} > Co^{2+} > Mg^{2+}$. This is in agreement with that of Irving and Williams⁴.

Acknowledgement

The authors record their sincere thanks to Dr. D. G. Vartak, B. A. R. C., Bombay for valuable suggestions.

References

1. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
2. H. A. FLASCHKA, "EDTA Titrations", Pergamon Press, Inc., N. Y., 1959.
3. M. S. MAYADEO and H. S. HUSSAIN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, 56, 143.
4. H. IRVING and R. J. P. WILLIAMS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3192.

Electrode Kinetics of the Polarographic Reduction of Ni(II) in the Presence of Increasing Concentrations of L-4-Hydroxyproline and L-Tryptophan

J. C. KHATRI and MUKHTAR SINGH

Department of Chemistry, Agra College, Agra-282 002

Manuscript received 12 January 1981, revised 12 April 1982, accepted 7 June 1982

THOUGH a few polarographic data^{1,2} on the electroreduction of Ni(II) in the presence of tryptophan are mentioned in literature, systematic and comprehensive studies on the electrode kinetics of this system are lacking. Besides, studies on the electrode kinetics of Ni(II) in the presence of L-4-hydroxyproline (LHP) have not been reported so far. The present paper aims at studying the influence of increasing concentrations of LHP and L-tryptophan on the kinetics of electrode reaction of Ni(II) under different conditions of pH.

Experimental

Solutions of $Ni(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ and $NaClO_4$ were prepared from reagent grade (A. R., B. D. H.) chemicals in conductivity water. L-4-Hydroxyproline (LHP) was a Fluka (Puriss, CHR) product, and L-tryptophan was a Reanal (Hungary) A. R. product and their aqueous solutions were used. The concentration of the depolarizer was kept at $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ in each case and that of supporting electrolyte ($NaClO_4$) at 0.1 M. Requisite amount of Triton X-100 was added to suppress the maximum.

Polarograms of the solutions were taken at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ by a manual set up (Toshniwal polarograph, Model CLO2 in conjunction with a Toshniwal polyflex galvanometer, Model PL 50). Purified nitrogen gas was passed through the solutions to remove the dissolved oxygen. Saturated calomel electrode (S.C.E.) was used as a reference electrode. The number of electrons, n , involved in the reduction process was determined by millicoulometric method of DeVries and Kroon³. This gave the value of n equal to 2 in each case. Having known the value of n , the Ilkovic equation was used to calculate the value of D at different concentrations of LHP and L-tryptophan. The potential-dependent rate constant, $k_{f,h}$, was calculated by Koutecky's method⁴. The kinetic parameters, αn_a and $k_{f,h}^0$, were calculated from the plots of $\log k_{f,h}$ vs $E_{d.e.}$. Throughout the measurements the current at the end of the drop (i.e. the maximum current) was recorded for the reasons given by Meites⁵.

The d.m.e. had the following capillary characteristics (in 0.1 M NaClO₄, open circuit): (i) for Ni(II)-LHP system: $m=2.46$ mg/sec; $t=2.44$ sec; $m^{2/3} t^{1/6}=2.11$ mg^{2/3} sec^{-1/6}; $h_{o.o.r.}=61.8$ cm; (ii) for Ni(II)-L-tryptophan system; $m=1.67$ mg/sec; $t=4.04$ sec; $m^{2/3} t^{1/6}=1.78$ mg^{2/3} sec^{-1/6}; $h_{o.o.r.}=63.0$ cm.

Results and Discussion

(i) Ni(II)-L-hydroxyproline (LHP) system :

(a) At constant pH 4; Ni(II) gives a single well-defined diffusion-controlled wave in the absence of LHP. With the addition of $2 \times 10^{-3} M$ LHP a second small wave appears at a more negative potential (-1.1 V vs S.C.E.) whose half-wave potential is -1.22 V (S.C.E.). On further increasing the concentration ($6 \times 10^{-3} M - 4 \times 10^{-2} M$) the $E_{1/2}$ of the second wave remains the same but at $[LHP] \geq 6 \times 10^{-2} M$, the $E_{1/2}$ becomes -1.27 V (S.C.E.). The wave-heights of both the waves are diffusion-controlled as revealed by the linearity of i_a vs $h_{o.o.r.}^{1/2}$ plots which pass through the origin. Analysis of these waves by log plots shows that both are irreversible. The more positive (first) wave may be attributed to aquo nickel ion and the second one to some complex species of nickel ion with LHP. This view is supported by the work of Pleticha⁶ who obtained two waves for Ni(II) in the presence of histidine, D-arginine and methionine; the more positive wave was attributed by him to uncomplexed nickel. As pointed out above, at higher concentrations ($\geq 6 \times 10^{-2} M$) of LHP the second wave is shifted to more negative potentials. A likely explanation of this may be that upto a certain concentration of LHP ($4 \times 10^{-2} M$) only one form of Ni(II)-LHP complex is present as a result of interaction between LHP and Ni(II), but at higher concentrations ($> 6 \times 10^{-2} M$) of LHP, a second species of complex is formed due to availability of excess ligand.

(b) At constant pH 8: In the absence of LHP, a single well-defined diffusion-controlled wave of aquo nickel ion is obtained. However, in the

presence of $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ LHP two well-defined waves appear which are diffusion-controlled and irreversible. $E_{1/2}$ of the first wave corresponds to the aquo nickel ion and that of the second more negative wave ($E_{1/2} = -1.22$ V vs S.C.E.) corresponds to some complex species of Ni(II) with LHP. On further increasing the concentration of LHP ($2 \times 10^{-3} - 8 \times 10^{-2} M$) the height of the first wave decreases while that of the second one increases thereby suggesting the participation of more and more nickel ion in the complex formation due to excess availability of the ligand. At still higher concentration of LHP ($10 \times 10^{-2} M$), the first wave disappears and only the more negative second wave persists whose $E_{1/2}$ is now shifted to more negative potential (-1.27 V vs S.C.E.). On increasing the concentration of LHP beyond $10 \times 10^{-2} M$, the $E_{1/2}$ of this wave records a negative shift. The fact that $E_{1/2}$ of the second wave changes from -1.22 V (upto $8 \times 10^{-2} M$ LHP) to -1.27 V (at $10 \times 10^{-2} M$ LHP) and then to ≈ 1.37 V (at LHP concentration $> 4 \times 10^{-2} M$) clearly shows the existence of consecutively formed complex species of Ni(II) with LHP.

(c) Influence of increasing concentrations of LHP on the kinetics of irreversible electrode reaction of Ni(II): On applying various tests of irreversibility⁷⁻¹⁰ it has been ascertained that the well-established irreversible electrode reaction of Ni(II) remains the same at pH 4 and 8. As the wave-heights of the second wave at constant pH 4 are comparatively very small, an analysis of kinetic parameters for this wave to a greater degree of precision is not possible. Likewise, the analysis of kinetic data in respect of the first wave at constant pH 8 has not been taken up. Only the kinetic parameters at concentrations of LHP $> 10 \times 10^{-2} M$, where single wave appears, have been calculated at this pH.

At constant pH 4, αn_a increases at lower concentrations ($\leq 6 \times 10^{-3} M$) of LHP while at higher concentrations ($\geq 10 \times 10^{-3} M$) it decreases. This shows that¹¹⁻¹³ the irreversible electrode reaction of Ni(II) becomes less irreversible at lower concentrations of LHP while it tends to become more irreversible at higher concentrations. An increase in the value of rate constant, $k_{f,h}^0$, at lower concentrations of LHP and a decrease in its value at higher concentrations support the above conclusions. At constant pH 8, αn_a and $k_{f,h}^0$ decrease with increasing concentrations of LHP thereby showing that the irreversible electrode reaction of Ni(II) tends to become more irreversible in the presence of increasing concentrations of LHP.

(ii) Ni(II)-L-tryptophan system: Ni(II) yields a single well-defined diffusion-controlled and irreversible wave in the presence of increasing amounts of L-tryptophan under different conditions of pH, viz., constant pH 4 and 7. At constant pH 7, a sharp maximum appeared on the plateau of C-V curves which, however, disappeared on the addition of 0.002% Triton X-100.

On applying various tests of irreversibility, it has been ascertained that the well-established irrever-

sible electrode reaction of Ni(II) remains the same under both the two conditions of pH. Under the two conditions of pH the rate constant, k_p^n , decreases with increasing concentrations of tryptophan. It follows from this that the irreversible electrode reaction of Ni(II) is rendered increasingly more irreversible as the concentration of tryptophan is increased. The parameter αn_a also decreases with increasing concentrations of tryptophan under different conditions of pH. The polarographic reduction of Ni(II) is a well-established 2-electron reduction process and therefore n_a , the number of electrons involved in the rate determining step, can either be 1 or 2. Since the decrease in αn_a values is indiscrete and at no stage the two consecutive values differ by a factor of 2, the possibility of a decrease in the value of the product αn_a due to a change in n_a may be ruled out. Thus it can be safely concluded that it is α which is decreasing. α , the transfer coefficient, signifies¹³ the fraction of the applied voltage which favours the cathodic reaction, $\text{Ni}^{2+} + 2e \rightarrow \text{Ni}$. A decrease in the value of α thus implies that the transfer of electron/electrons is made increasingly difficult. In other words, the electrode reaction of Ni(II) is rendered increasingly more irreversible as the concentration of L-tryptophan is increased. Thus, the variations in the values of both the kinetic parameters point to the same conclusion.

References

1. S. CHANDRA and S. N. SRIVASTAVA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1969, 7, 829.
2. S. LAL and G. D. CHRISTAN, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1971, 313, 99.
3. T. DEVRIES and J. L. KROON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 2484.
4. J. KOUTECKY, *Chem. Listy*, 1953, 47, 323; *Colln. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1953, 18, 597; J. KOUTECKY and J. CIZEK, *Coll. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1956, 21, 836.
5. L. MEITES, "Polarographic Techniques", Interscience Publ., New York, 1965, p. 241.
6. R. PLETICHA, *Colln. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1950, 15, 807; *Chem. Listy*, 1951, 45, 185.
7. L. MEITES, "Polarographic Techniques", Interscience Publ., New York, 1965, p. 232.
8. R. GOTO and I. TACHI, *Proc. Intern. Polarogr. Congr.*, Prague, 1951, 1, 69.
9. P. DELAHAY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 4944.
10. P. KIVALO, K. B. OLDHAM and H. A. LAITINEN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 4148.
11. S. S. SHARMA, S. K. JHA and M. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1977, 15A, 742.
12. S. S. SHARMA, S. K. JHA and M. SINGH, *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1977, 32b, 416.
13. S. K. JHA, S. JHA and S. N. SRIVASTAVA, *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1975, 30b, 859.

Reactivity of Indian Rock Phosphates in Presence of Oxidative Degradation Products of Coal

D. N. PATHAK

Department of Chemistry, Regional Institute of Technology, Jamshedpur-831 014

Manuscript received 1 November 1980, revised 20 October 1981
accepted 28 April 1982

THE oxidative degradation products of coal, obtained by the action of potassium permanganate in presence of rock phosphate in aqueous solution, increase the reactivity of rock phosphates

resulting in the dissolution of more phosphatic content in water.

A variety of oxidizing agents, mostly in acidic medium, were used in the past for controlled low temperature degradation of coal¹. Later, oxidation of coal in alkaline medium using potassium permanganate was studied in detail²⁻⁶. The different parameters upon which the oxidative degradation of coal in alkaline medium is dependent was investigated very recently by Banerji⁷. Contradictory reports^{8,9} on the reactivity of Indian rock phosphates posed a great problem of its utility to chemists all over the world. The work of Johnston¹⁰ on the dissolution of insoluble phosphate in aqueous solutions of organic acids prompted the author to design the present investigation for determining the extent of reactivity by water soluble organic acids produced in the oxidative degradation of coal by potassium permanganate in presence of rock phosphates.

Experimental

Rock phosphates from Rajasthan, Uttar Pradesh and Bihar, obtained through Geological Survey of India, were powdered, sieved (100 mesh, B.S.S.) and analysed according to the procedure of Washington¹¹.

A number of stoppered conical flasks were taken and 1g finely powdered sample of each rock phosphate, 0.5 g coal (dmf, 36 mesh BSS, C=80%) and 100 ml 0.1 N KMnO₄ solution were added in each of the flasks. The flasks with their contents were kept agitated in a mechanical shaker at room temperature (27°). After definite intervals of time the solution of each flask was allowed to stand for some time, filtered and washed with water through a sintered glass crucible. Aliquot portions were utilized for determining P₂O₅ and for measuring the extent of oxidative degradation¹². A blank (mineral + water) estimation was also simultaneously carried out.

Phosphate was estimated volumetrically after precipitating with ammonium molybdate solution.

In order to measure the extent of oxidative degradation, a suitable portion of the aliquot was treated with solid KI and acidified with conc. HCl. The liberated iodine was titrated against a standard thiosulphate solution using starch as an indicator. Permanganate consumed by coal in different time intervals was calculated from the titre values.

Results and Discussion

The analysis (Table 1) shows that the rock phosphates contain varying amounts of P₂O₅ (12 to 30%), magnesium and iron, suitable for healthy plant growth. It is interesting to record that all the rock phosphates are alkaline in aqueous solutions.

The experimental results (Tables 2 and 3) show that the release of phosphate from rock phosphates by water is not much. However, with water soluble aromatic polycarboxylic acids, produced as a result of degradation of coal by oxidizing action of alkaline